

D7.2 Updated Communications Dissemination and Sustainability Plan & Initial Report

29.04.2024

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Details

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01

Introduction

This Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan (CDS) under Work Package 7 has been created by WP7 lead Momentum in the framework of the **Accelerate Future HEI** project. It outlines our roadmap to maximising the communications and dissemination performance and sustainability of the project.

Under the guidance of Momentum, **Accelerate Future HEI** will operate a robust and sustained dissemination campaign throughout the 48 months of the project to share results and encourage their use with all key target audiences. Dissemination and communications will be a planned process providing information to the relevant target group and key actors regarding the project process, activities, and results using different dissemination channels at local, national, and EU levels.

Momentum acknowledges the importance of collaboration and inclusivity in achieving the project's objectives. Therefore, we wholeheartedly invite and value the feedback of all partners on this Communications Dissemination and Sustainability Plan.

Context

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) can have a strong positive impact on regional and Europe-wide social and economic development through education, research and engagement. However, they require targeted, methodological and experienced support to enhance their capability to fully realise their potential.

Accelerate Future HEI responds to the above-mentioned needs through the development and testing of acceleration services to support HEIs institutional transformation.

Key Objectives

TO IDENTIFY

the status quo of the HEI and its ecosystem regarding entrepreneurial and innovative activities.

TO DEVELOP

test and implement acceleration services that help institutions undertake a transformation roadmap and projects.

TO BUILD

the capacity of the participating HEIs staff to implement the transformation roadmaps through a **skills development program**.

TO EVALUATE

the strategies from HEIs supervised by an 'acceleration board' of **independent experts**.

TO GENERATE

policy feedback to the European Commission as well as provide widespread dissemination of the pilot results to other target groups.

Scope of the Plan

This document acts as a guideline for all project partners to drive their dissemination activities, both offline and online not only during the project but also in a way that will sustain the project beyond its four year duration. It ensures continuous communication of the project activities, milestones and results. Our plan will be supplemented by regular dissemination ‘boosts’, and planned updates that respond to new opportunities with specific and updated marketing tactics over the four-year lifetime of the project.

The Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan will ensure maximum visibility of the project through tailored communication activities and by employing tools that address different stakeholders along the communication chain, to raise awareness about the potential of **Accelerate Future HEI** and reach out to society and show the impact and benefits. It will disseminate **Accelerate Future HEI** results to relevant stakeholders to engage the community and be active in transferring knowledge and results. Furthermore, it will identify the potential different routes for innovation and exploitation of the project results to maximise, scale and sustain the post-project impact on a large range of stakeholders.

A successful Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan implies that all different members of the target groups of the project are addressed through the proper channel(s) and can obtain information concerning the project activities that are of their interest and that they can get involved in. The Dissemination and Sustainability Plan focuses on the necessary media to be used to reach the identified target groups and maximise the impact of the project results.

Meet the Team

Samantha Carty
EU Project Specialist

Samantha is our lead on Horizon, Erasmus + Knowledge Alliances and Erasmus Alliances for Innovation projects, which bring higher education institutions and businesses together to work on common issues. Through this work, Momentum partners with over 50 leading HEI education bodies across Europe.

Gillian Keane
Head of Design

Since 2007, Gillian has been Momentum's graphic designer. With nearly 20 years' experience in the design/print industry, she is responsible for the development and presentation of brand proposals, learning materials design, web-based graphics and visual multimedia content for digital marketing.

Denise Callan, EU Project and Communications Specialist

A graduate of UCD and NUIM, Denise has worked in Rural Development, Tourism & Culture, Education and Marketing with Public Sector, SMEs and major national and international brands. She builds on Momentum's work in enabling innovative collaboration between Industry and Higher Education and on Horizon Europe research and innovation projects, ensuring this valuable work can make an impact.

Leon Quinn, WordPress Web Developer and Multimedia Specialist

A freelance web developer and digital design expert since 2002, Leon has been using WordPress from its inception. He graduated from TU with a BSc in Digital Technology, Design & Innovation. Other specialties include; Photoshop, Audio/Video editing, Podcasting, Search Engine Optimisation and Music Production.

Contact our Accelerate Future HEI team at Samantha@Momentumconsulting.ie

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Key Activities

What is a Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan?

The overall objectives of the WP 7 Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan are:

- To **create awareness and understanding** of the importance of Entrepreneurial and Innovative Universities.
- To **raise awareness** about acceleration services and methodologies.
- **Support the integration** of all stakeholders in the different phases of the project.
- **Widely disseminate** the project results and outputs.
- **Set the foundation** for further implementation/exploitation of the results of the project.

We understand Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability as follows;

Why have a Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan?

Whenever we talk about communicating and disseminating project results, we refer to activities intended to ensure that results are appropriately recognised, proven and implemented on a wide scale to ensure the sustainability of the project.

Having a plan can help achieve objectives in three ways: -

1. **Creating Awareness**

Enable our key target audiences to become aware of our work on the project. They do not require detailed knowledge of our work, but it is helpful for them to be aware of Accelerate Future HEI activities and outcomes. Creating such awareness will help 'word of mouth' dissemination and help us build an identity and profile within our target communities.

2. **Promoting Understanding**

Our key target groups/ stakeholders that we will directly target as part of our dissemination actions as we know they will benefit from our offerings. It is important that this group will develop a deeper understanding of our project's work.

3. **Prompting Action**

Action refers to a change in practice resulting from the adoption of Accelerate Future HEI outputs and approaches. Our target audience in this phase will acquire the skills, knowledge, and influence to bring about change within their organisations.

What role do partners play in Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability?

Momentum integrates all project partners as well as UIIN and TUMint's wide-reaching networks into their communications and dissemination activities to ensure a wider-reaching and long-lasting impact of the project. All twelve project partners contribute to these activities.

Led by UIIN, the project unites international experts on developing and supporting acceleration services, together with two established HEI consortia. UIIN will work with Acceleration Partners Momentum and TUMInt. to design the overall methodology for acceleration services which will be tested by the HEI consortia: INCORE (EIT HEI Initiative) and E.I.N.S (EIT HEI Initiative) as well as a European University Alliance E³UDRES².

Acceleration Partners

UIIN – Lead partner
TUM International
Momentum

Testing Partners

INCORE consortium:

Instituto Superior Tecnico (IST, Portugal)
Université de La Reunion (UR, France)
Universidad Europea de Canarias (UEC, Spain)
Universidade da Madeira (Uma Portugal)

E.I.N.S. consortium:

St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS, Germany)
UC Leuven-Limburg University of Applied Sciences (UCLL, Belgium)
Hungarian University of Agriculture & Life Sciences (MATE, Hungary)
Politehnica University Timisoara (UPT, Romania)
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA, Latvia)

Outreach, exploitation and communication activities defined for the project are administered concurrently at two levels: regional and an overarching transnational level as a part of WP7 Dissemination. The dissemination activities on the transnational level will be administered by Momentum, whereas the regional and national levels fall into the responsibility of each partner institution communicating and disseminating information in their regions through their institutional channels to local stakeholders and target groups.

All project partners, including UIIN's wide-reaching network, will be integrated into communications and dissemination efforts and activities to ensure a wider-reaching impact of the project to reach internal and external stakeholders and ensure the sustainability of the project.

What are we Communicating and Disseminating?

Accelerate Future HEI is a programme of support and training for HEI transformation to help Institutions focus and amplify their capabilities, and realise their potential, to recognise and drive knowledge and innovation opportunities that impact regional and Europe-wide social and economic development through education, research and engagement.

The Accelerate Future HEI Transformation Agenda will reinforce HEIs' role as drivers of regional and European ecosystems enabling shared objectives between the EU and Member States' initiatives to support HEIs in their efforts to transform their activities and service to society missions.

The **Accelerate Future HEI** project will develop, implement and disseminate a holistic, standardised yet contextually flexible methodology for EU, national and regional actions and investment measures to help strengthen the symbiosis between the HEI and its region.

The main project deliverables from WP1 – WP7 over 4 years are:

Main Deliverables

Management, QA & Policy Feedback M1 – M48				
<i>The plan for how we will ensure we deliver on our outcomes & inform policy</i>				
D1.1 DMP M6	D1.2 Initial policy briefing M12	D1.3 Interim policy briefing M30	D1.4 Final policy recommendations report M48	

Current State Analysis M1 – M12		Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs M6-M18		Acceleration services pilot-testing M12 – M48	
<i>Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation. Where are HEIs now?</i>		<i>What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?</i>		<i>What will you test and implement?</i>	
D2.1 Strategic Vision Statements – M12	D2.2 Synthesis Report – M12	D3.1 Roadmaps Analysis report – Draft M12	D3.2 Roadmaps Analysis report – Final M18	D4.1 Summary report – common ITAP issues M12	D4.2 Case study report- ITAPs and results M48

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program M1 – M48		
<i>The plan for how HEIs gain skills and insights for acceleration & transformation</i>		
D5.1 Program overview & delivery plan M12	D5.2 Program delivery progress report & updated plan M30	D5.3 Summary of the learning outcomes M48

Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation M1 – M48		
<i>We will monitor progress and evaluate impact of ITAPs</i>		
D6.1 Monitoring & evaluation plan – M12	D6.2 ITAPs Progress report – M30	D6.3 Final Impact Report

Communication and Dissemination M1 – M48			
<i>We plan to share our key learnings so others can benefit</i>			
D7.1 Initial Plan M6	D7.2 Updated plan and initial dissemination report M12	D7.3 Interim dissemination report M30	D7.4 Final dissemination report M48

Excellent communication and dissemination rely on excellent content

- Identifying and publishing individual reports for each stakeholder and one synthesis report to understand the current state and desired future state of each testing partner and provide an evidence base for entrepreneurial and innovative activities. **(WP2)** Reports on surveys and focus group interviews, which can be prepared as qualitative reports with attractive visuals highlighting the most important information will be valuable for internal communication of those involved in the University and help to communicate about the project’s next steps.
- Development of a future roadmap for institutional transformation and Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs) of each of the testing partners about entrepreneurial and innovative activities. **(WP3)**
- Each testing partner develops their investment strategy based on the insights and guidance received from coaching and four dedicated online development workshops. **(WP4)**
- Creation of learning experiences in the form of “How to” Accelerate Training workshops as well as peer-learning and networking-focused cohort knowledge exchange events.
- Workshops will be designed and delivered to define, capture and evaluate the progress of the ITAPs.
- Each testing partner will create short interim reports after each impact-capturing workshop using specially designed reporting templates. **(WP5)**
- A set of guidelines for defining KPIs and progress indicators will be designed, as well as an agenda for the impact-capturing workshop series. **(WP6)**

WP 7 underpins all of these activities and the dissemination deliverables will specifically focus on four outputs over the 4 year duration.

Communication and Dissemination opportunities are grounded in our main deliverables.

Deliverables		Due Date
D7.1	Initial Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Plan	M6
D7.2	Updated Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Plan & Initial Report	M12
D7.3	Interim Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Report	M30
D7.4	Final Interim Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Report	M48

Stakeholders and Target Groups

Promotion and awareness-raising is an important part of the communications and dissemination process. It is key the project is delivered to its primary target audiences. Target audiences will be engaged with messages that will be specifically tailored to them.

The **Accelerate Future HEI** project includes primary target groups and stakeholders of influence who will participate in and benefit from the project. To generate and exploit the maximum value of the project, this Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan is responsive to the needs of our key target groups, and focuses on the respective channels, and multipliers to reach the target groups, the material and messages delivered, as well as the type and frequency of the communication intended.

The project methodology and underlying processes predefine the development of open-access methodologies and a showcase of results. With these open-access deliverables, we aim to create a direct impact on the stakeholder groups outside of the testing HEI partners.

CORE TARGET GROUPS

- HEI Testing Partners
 - HEI Leadership
- Non-academic/Professional Staff
- Academic Staff/Lecturers/Researcher
 - Students & Life-Long Learners

EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS

- Other HEIs (national, regional, local and European levels)
 - Industrial partners, SMEs and startups
- Public bodies (Local, regional, national and European), including municipalities, departments of education, governmental support offices for higher education/entrepreneurship/regional development, etc. Network organisations (local, regional, national and European) entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem drivers Policy makers, policy advocates and thought leaders

Using the ADKAR Model

To activate the relevant stakeholders and attract sufficient attention to the project activities and outputs across partners countries and internationally, we adapt the change management methodology enabling a gradual instilling of desired mindset shift - the Prosci ADKAR® Model (Awareness, Desire, Knowledge & Ability, Reinforcement).

This Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan (CDS Plan) aligns with the ADKAR model to define the project parameters and its objectives, benefits, and impacts, identify key stakeholders and audiences, and segment them based on their roles, needs, and preferences. Additionally, we will assess the level of awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement of each audience segment, and design and deliver communications accordingly. We will also track the progress and outcomes of our communication efforts and identify any issues or opportunities for improvement.

With ADKAR as the basis for the project's outreach, communication, dissemination and sustainability strategy, we want to help the participating institutions to:

- 1: Create general awareness and interest in the mission of Accelerate Future HEI.
- 2: Raise their internal and external stakeholders' awareness about the importance of an entrepreneurial approach inside and outside the university.
- 3: Fuel the desire to participate in the activities that lead to a more entrepreneurial culture within and outside the university.
- 4: Provide knowledge and further build the capability to drive entrepreneurial change by other European HEIs interested in transformation through active exploitation of the project's open resources.
- 5: Promote and reinforce the entrepreneurial change in the higher education landscape through opening dialogues (civic and policy) with various stakeholders. Recognising the importance of aligning our communication approaches, we address internal and external stakeholders using different approaches.

CDS Plan Schedule

Initial awareness phase (M1-6):

- establishment of the project website
- identification of communication and dissemination opportunities
- creation of basic tools incl. graphical identity (i.e., logo, templates for documents and presentations)
- consolidation of a stakeholder database to optimize targeted communication and dissemination.

Targeted dissemination phase (M6-36):

- the consortium will enrich the website
- publish a brochure
- issue the first press release
- attend selected events
- Preliminary project results will be presented to the target audiences
- Partner dissemination reports every 6 months M6 –M48
- Impact assessment is crucial at this stage to monitor and reorient the strategy if necessary.

Presentation of results (M36-48):

This represents the period closely before the end of the project when the project reaches its most significant outputs. This phase will be focused on informing the target audience for the exploitation. This will be the more active period in the whole PCDE.

Awareness

Phase 1: Raise Awareness amongst HEI internal and external stakeholders about the importance of an entrepreneurial approach inside and outside of the university.

Building Awareness is the first phase of our approach and will run from Month 1 as we seek to build up an engaged community around Accelerate Future HEI. Our tactics will include:

Brand Building

Momentum has created a strong professional and engaging project brand and intent tagline. This is the first step in the visibility creation of the project under our Communication ambition. The brand is also available in an animated format, as presented on the project website:

<https://acceleratefuturehei.eu/>

Key brand features include: -

- Text-based brands are known to lead to brand longevity. The brand emphasises the word accelerate, and the future-focused project ambition by using an upward forward-facing arrow design.
- The colour combination of red and black balances positive energy balanced with intent. The primary colour red gives positive energy while black adds certainty and authority.
- Our brand is leading out on a series of design templates and promotional materials (flyers, logos, signs and banners).
- Our brand guidelines will be used by project partners to ensure brand consistency across: -
 - Brand and brand usage
 - Colour specifications
 - Typography
 - Use of trademark symbols

The first phase of marketing collateral will be created (months 1 to 6), and will encompass a series of marketing tools that will allow us to reach large audiences in a short period of time. To include:-

- Brand Manual
- 1-page project summary.
- 5 slides project presentation, in editable PowerPoint format and created as an introductory video
- Project brochure (awareness building theme) * to illustrate key project concepts using infographics and visual aids. The project brochure will be uploaded in electronic PDF format onto the project website as from its production and it will be easy to download and share.
- Infographics summarising the project results as are striving for – Our Ambition at a Glance
- Project roll-up banner
- Project e-zine template.
- Project reports template.
- Event-specific project flyers, for various events
- Online banners to include branded social media headers, placeholders etc. *
- Graphics to support partner dissemination e.g., our badge of honour

All WP 7 shared content can be found at the following link for the duration of the project: [WP7](#)

Obligations for recipients of EU funding programmes 2021-2027

Since 2021, all recipients of EU funds have the legal obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding to ensure visibility and transparency.

Momentum will ensure that Accelerate Future HEI explicitly acknowledges that it has received EU funding as part of the Horizon EU funding programme 2021-2027 to ensure visibility and transparency and will follow the obligations as set out here to display the emblem and funding statement: [Communicating about your EU-funded project \(europa.eu\)](#)

**Funded by
the European Union**

Consistent Use of Branded Graphics in Calls to Action

Momentum will create a series of branded templates that will support partners to bring attention to key project actions. The templates will be created in PowerPoint so that they are easily editable for individual partner use. An example of this approach is the invitation to join future state focus groups.

**accelerate
future HEI**
supporting future focused higher education

Welcome to **Accelerate Future HEI**, a unique opportunity to develop more entrepreneurial and innovative higher education institutions.

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) can positively impact regional and Europe-wide social and economic development through education, research and engagement. To do this, HEIs require targeted support to enhance their capability to fully realise their potential. Accelerate Future HEI will develop and test acceleration services, to equip HEIs with the skills and capacity to drive their institutional transformation to become more entrepreneurial and innovative.

YOU ARE INVITED TO JOIN OUR DESIRED FUTURE STATE FOCUS GROUP

To collectively discuss and visualise the future state of innovation and entrepreneurship at your university.

Who is invited?

- HEI or Faculty leadership, middle management, Deans and Heads of Departments.
- Professional and administrative staff responsible for supporting activities and areas of external engagement, innovation and entrepreneurship.
- Academic staff and researchers involved in entrepreneurship, engagement and innovation.

In this interactive session, we will guide you through a structured canvas and work collaboratively to envisage how the different elements of the entrepreneurial and innovative university could look for the University.

Agenda

- Vision and Objectives (30 mins)
- The Entrepreneurial & Innovative University in terms of:
 1. **Activities** in education, research, commercialisation, management
 2. **Mindset** of academics, professional staff, management and students
 3. **Organisation** including incentives, support structures, institutional commitment, and support services
 4. **Impact & ecosystem** including external support mechanisms, role within the ecosystem, impact measurement and monitoring & evaluation (2 hours)
- Final reflections & wrap up (30 mins)

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Project Website

Momentum has established an engaging project website <https://acceleratefuturehei.eu/> reflecting our corporate design. The website is the central access point for the project. All data generated during the course of the project will be made available through a project website- which will be continuously updated.

The project website will spread awareness and share information about the project and will be kept active for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

The main features of the website are: -

- A dynamic and engaging landing page and a selection of subpages highlighting the main information about the project and contact details of the partners.
- Mobile friendly design
- Use of best practice web development, SEO optimisation, integration with different media formats, e.g., infographics, videos, and presentations to create a dynamic intuitive environment for all visitors.
- Incorporation of resources repository with all materials and outputs of the project in easily downloadable format.
- Source of downloadable marketing materials (e.g., posters, flyers) to equip all stakeholders to promote the project outcomes and both training programmes and toolkits.
- Publish annual mini-e-zine series available for free download. Four issues to be published during the project lifetime.
- Publishing articles about the main project outputs, content and promotion of the training programmes, and project events will occur on the project website.
- All WP deliverables will be available for download and form the basis of dissemination activity via shorter engaging articles and posts.

The project website will be updated regularly by Momentum to keep visitors engaged by highlighting recent news within the scope of the project from global and European outlets.

Social Media

Dedicated social media platforms (Twitter, LinkedIn) will be kept active on a frequent basis by posting news about the project and sharing the news from external news channels within the thematic scope of the project to build awareness with stakeholders.

Partners can assist with target audience recruitment and identifying social media accounts to engage with. Each participating project partner will be included in social media posting, including associated alliances @incore_eu @eudres_alliance @REA_research @HorizonEU

LinkedIn The following LinkedIn page has been set up [Accelerate Future HEI: Overview | LinkedIn](#)

Twitter The following Twitter account has been set up [AccelerateFutureHEI \(@AccFutureHEI\) / Twitter](#)

We will use the following Hashtags in social media posts to help amplify our messaging.

#AccFutureHEI
#HorizonEU
#highereducationinnovation
#REA (research executive agency)

As part of the social media strategy, we will ensure:

Project partners are steered towards a unified approach to strategic social media sharing and tagging in their expansive networks that will contribute to building our project visibility. To achieve this, a detailed professional 'Social Media Content Kit' will be shared with the partners that will inform them about the key target groups (including their specific interests and values), type of content (short and long copy), frequency of posting and key hashtags, design, style, and length of the language to be used for each of the social media channels.

Social media links will be provided from the main page of the project website. to keep visitors updated with real-time information and the opportunity to share and reshare the latest developments of the project.

Calls to action to follow the Accelerate Future HEI social media accounts will be published on the project brochures and flyers.

Social media is designed for conversation, not for announcements. To be effective, we have committed to regularly posting across our channels and engaging in topic-based contributions as appropriate. We encourage everyone involved in the project to join in the conversation so that multiple points of view are reflected.

Multimedia Content

As we prioritise digital media content and approaches, Momentum will create a short promotional video introducing the project, our partnership, and our activities. Additional promotional videos and short-form video content will be produced at key stages of the project to utilise this visual media to share updates and flag activities and events. A series of nine short videos about transformation (one per testing partner) will be created. Attractive videos will be posted on the project website and relayed through YouTube and LinkedIn platforms for maximum visibility. Where appropriate, Momentum will add podcasts and audio material as well as host virtual events through the website to ensure a mix of multimedia content throughout the project's lifetime

Infographics

A series of nine infographics about Transformation implemented by testing partners (1 per testing partner) will be created as part of this project, to highlight the reach of acceleration services towards Entrepreneurial and Innovative Universities in Europe

PHASE 1 AWARENESS BUILDING ACTIONS

- 1) Website launch supported by press releases for partners to use across all channels.
- 2) Website monthly updates by Momentum to include news, new documents to be made available for download, information on events etc.
- 3) Image bank - Collect and provide access to license free images to reflect the specific target groups.
- 4) Momentum will create a specific Social Media Content Kit for Twitter and LinkedIn.
- 5) Partners to contribute to profiling their Reach Database – see Appendix 1, sharing details of their dissemination reach.
- 6) All partners will contribute to the development and update of the project website blog and news section, highlighting the developments within the scope of the project in their region. Partners will translate the content for dissemination for national purposes.
- 7) Each partner will display the news about the project on their respective official websites and include the news about the project and project's developments into their newsletters at least once in 6 months to reach their regional stakeholders.

Desire

Phase 2: Fuel the Desire to participate in the activities that lead to a more entrepreneurial culture within and outside the university.

In the second phase of the ADKAR approach, we will create desire amongst our target groups to participate in the programme activities. This is where dissemination comes to life. Establishing consistent communication with target groups via our partner's extensive contact databases will be key for a pan-European approach. In this way, rather than trying to build the **Accelerate Future HEI** community from the ground up, we can benefit from already existing communities and build upon those. These include social media communities (i.e. UIIN, TUM Int., MMS, UE, UPT, MATE, UMA, UCLL, STPUAS, UR, IST, ViA), EU-level networks (INCORE, EU3DRES2, EINS and European Research Executive Agency & Horizon Europe), and country-level networks. By tapping into these channels and sharing the project's activities/outputs we will increase the outreach to the target groups (e.g., universities, academics, researchers, students, industry, etc.)

Accelerate Future HEI Ezine Series

Momentum will prepare the guidelines for and create the annual **Accelerate Future HEI** ezine. Four issues will be published during the project lifetime (M12, M24, M36, M48) to include the aim and scope of the project, target groups, topics, content (e.g., news, events, case studies, interviews, or research results) also marketing channels and design.

The Ezine series will be circulated directly and available for download in PDF format with open access. Across channel marketing, social media will promote the publication of the Ezine editions through blogs and publications. The publication series will be widely spread via partner newsletters and channels, project subscribers updates, project social media, the project website as well as an external resource/news-sharing platforms. While partners and their networks will be core disseminators, we invite partners to suggest additional platforms. These publications will:

- (1) communicate the project activities and
- (2) generate awareness for the general topic of HEIs growth challenges and strategies
- (3) inform about the received project results.

Momentum will create a design template and all partners will contribute content with relevant permissions. Each partner will report on the numbers in their contact database (See Appendix 1) and will send the ezine directly to their network.

European Commission Channels

The project will avail of the many European Commission free-of-charge services to support our dissemination and exploitation activities:

[Open Research Europe platform](#): An open-access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article revision.

[Horizon Results platform](#): A platform for showcasing your research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others.

[Horizon Results Booster](#): Free consulting services including a portfolio dissemination and exploitation strategy, business plan development and go-to-market support.

Success stories will be championed through some of the European Commission's free-of-charge channels such as:

- [Cordis Results in Brief](#),
- [CORDIScovery podcasts](#),
- [Research & innovation success storiesEN●●●](#)
- [Horizon Magazine](#) or
- during events such as the [R&I Days](#).

External Publications

Accelerate Future HEI will publish our project materials on pertinent 3rd party platforms, including but not limited to:

- Open Research Central
- LinkedIn
- Open Journal Systems
- Pluto
- Glasstree
- Science Media (publishing videos)
- Valor platform
- Orvium
- Yammer
- ResearchGate
- Open Science Network
- OpenEdition Books
- Welcome Open Research

Throughout the project, attempts will be made to reach out to like-minded networks, that may be interested in utilising and replicating the results of the project in each region and internationally. We also invite partners to suggest any other platforms that they feel are appropriate for this project.

Thought Leadership Blog Posts

Each partner will be charged with creating blog posts according to the schedule set out in Appendix 2. Partners will be able to update the project stakeholders through these blog articles which will be published bimonthly to highlight the ‘entrepreneurial university journey’. Momentum can also support partners to ensure visibility at conferences and events. We will also seek opinion pieces and interviews from the experts to highlight internal expertise and showcase these on the website. MMS and Partners will identify opportunities to engage with the target audience and build awareness through these activities.

In addition to publishing bi-monthly news, Momentum will:

- Create ezine guidelines and Design an e-zine template
- Collect ezine content from partners and external platforms

The annual ezines will showcase developments within the project and inspirational stories from the partners.

The project website will host transformation case studies developed by each HEI, as well as a series of webinars on entrepreneurial and engaged universities open to the wider public.

PHASE 2 DESIRE BUILDING ACTIONS

- Create Ezine guidelines and Design an Ezine template (Momentum)
- Collect Ezine content from partners and external platforms (Momentum)
- Blogs/Ezine Articles – internal and external authors requested.

Knowledge & Ability

Phase 3: Provide KNOWLEDGE and further build the CAPABILITY to drive entrepreneurial change by other European HEIs interested in transformation through active exploitation of the project's open resources

Momentum will contribute to WP5, ensuring that information on the Capacity Building and Knowledge Exchange elements of the project is shared e.g., blog posts, ezine articles, and social media posts.

Working Group Workshops

These thematic-based workshops will address some of the common areas that the testing partners will be working on during the ITAP, with the aim of sharing insights to support each other.

Knowledge Exchange Events

These 8 events bring the cohort together to create a shared knowledge base, share findings and learnings and create a virtual meeting place for the HEIs to connect with peers, and other ecosystem actors, including investors and public funders.

They can provide knowledge, and further build the capability to drive entrepreneurial change by other European HEIs interested in transformation, through active exploitation of the project's open resources.

Through dedicated policy workshops and by inviting key stakeholders of the European HE sector, as well as case studies developed by the Testing Partners, the methodology and the results of the pilot with the testing partners will be widespread. In addition, policy recommendations will be provided to the EC and Member States to inform future targeted and synergetic actions in support of HEIs.

Outreach Activities

A more proactive role by HEIs in their regional ecosystems and increased university-industry-society engagement practices means that ecosystem stakeholders will benefit from the knowledge exchange during the outreach activities organised by the stakeholders.

To support the outreach actions the project will:

- Publish all open access deliverables on the project website and EPALE platform
- Create infographics about transformation implemented by testing partners
- Develop videos about transformation implemented by testing partners
- Host a series of policy workshops to open to a wider group of participating HEI stakeholders.

Reinforcement

Phase 4: Promote and REINFORCE the entrepreneurial change in the higher education landscape through opening dialogues (civic and policy) with various stakeholders.

Momentum will ensure the project achieves impact beyond the duration of the project. The results of the pilot with the testing partners will be wide-spread, and policy recommendations will be provided to the EC and Member States to inform future targeted and synergetic actions in support of the HE sector.

Key outreach activities during this phase include:

- Promotion of the project deliverables to like-minded organisations
- Create a database of external stakeholders interested in the results of the project at its later stages
- Public webinars and policy workshop series organised by each partner institution

This project has the ability to scale up and ensure lasting impact through the outcomes and means created as part of it. It has the potential to promote and reinforce the entrepreneurial change in higher education landscape through opening dialogues (civic and policy) with various stakeholders.

Momentum will ensure that:

- Outputs are kept available online as long as there is a clear interest in them (a minimum of 3 years after the project's end).
- In order to increase its potential use, the project outputs will be kept as freely accessible resources for non-commercial purposes.

Outreach, exploitation and communication activities defined for the project are administered concurrently at both a regional and an overarching transnational level. The dissemination activities on the transnational level will be administered by Momentum, whereas the regional and national levels fall into the responsibility of each partner institution disseminating information in their regions through their institutional channels to local stakeholders and target groups.

All project partners, including UIIN's wide-reaching network, will be integrated into dissemination efforts and activities to ensure a wider-reaching impact of the project to reach internal and external stakeholders. Momentum will create internal and external materials to aid the promotion efforts of all partners in sharing project outputs.

03

Targets and Measuring Impact

Targets and Measuring Impact

Central to the project Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan is communicating the benefits and outcomes of the project and to ensure engagement with the key target groups, as well as with regional, national and international stakeholders for a long-lasting impact of the project. The project's Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability plan's success will be measured against the following criteria of evaluation:

- Proper use of communication channels and materials to reach the end user and target groups.
- Whether the target audiences were reached and engaged
- To what extent the project's results are known and used outside the project consortium
- How users and stakeholders judge the value of outputs.
- What impact are outputs having upon the practice and understanding of target audiences and what are the prospects for further impact in the future?
- To what extent has sustainability been secured, and external recognition achieved?

Metrics will be used to evaluate the real interactions stimulated by our communication activities. They will help to assess (1) how many people are recognising the project, (2) what people have a say about it, and (3) which target groups are most engaged. Here the social media communication metrics will be of high significance.

Reach is assessed by “Click-Through Rates” (CTR) applied to links and media. It measures how successful content has been in capturing the target group’s attention. The higher the CTR, the more successful the content has been in generating interest. Further indicators include the duration of stay, number of views, number of followers and response rate to invitations to download results and resources.

Engagement is assessed by making use of surveys to the target groups through monitoring work packages for quality and evaluation. The surveys provide the consortium with real-time insights into the health of stakeholder involvement. It will be an essential tool for measuring stakeholders’ engagement, as they give a snapshot of their feelings centred around specific questions. We apply additional indicators concerning social media, for instance,

- number of likes,
- shares and retweets/reposts including comments
- the number of downloads.

Dissemination Actions and Reporting

To realise and reinforce the overall dissemination of the Accelerate Future HEI project, as dissemination lead Momentum

- Welcomes the feedback of all partners on this plan
- Welcomes all feedback and input from partners in the creation and sharing of promotional materials.
- Requires all partners register their activities in a communication reporting document and share it with Momentum every 6 months. All partners should save evidence of the activities conducted throughout each phase. By performing regular monitoring of the activities, it is possible to assess if the action plan is being carried out properly. It will also be possible to see which activities had the biggest impact on the stakeholders (both in quantitative and qualitative terms).

This feedback and partner reporting will be considered for inclusion in the Dissemination Partner updates. All Appendices should be completed by partners and kept on the SharePoint link for continuous reference and review.

Sustainability

Sustainability

The Sustainability element of the Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability plan enables the Accelerate Future HEI Consortium to ensure the aims and objectives of the project are achieved with effective planning, communication and supervision between partners and stakeholders. It also defines and establishes the Sustainability Strategy for Accelerate Future HEI and the best way to exploit the project results and ensure the project is sustained in a recognisable format, after the funding period ends. For all the partners, the two workshops undertaken by UIIN, and this document are the signposts for further actions which should be undertaken to promote and exploit the results of the Accelerate Future HEI project.

Planning

Sustainability planning for the Accelerate Future HEI project is built on four main components:

Market Needs	Stakeholder needs are clearly identified and addressed in a target-oriented way.
People	People are put in the centre of the project.
Implementation	Implementation of results is made as easy as possible.
Structural	Right structures are put in place and can be maintained in an efficient way.

To ensure the long-term realisation of the project sustainability goals, communication of the project results from the partners to other stakeholders will begin during the lifetime of the project. After the project is completed, communication with the target groups will be maintained to build a solid base which can sustain the development of work experience after the lifetime of the project.

To achieve this, the consortium will implement the sustainability plan by:

- Raising awareness
- Sharing tools and resources
- Demonstrating the value of approaches with a very substantial body of users. As the target groups take up the opportunities, tools, and resources, their practice will then generate interest in the consultancy programmes and propagate waves of adoption across Europe.

Goals

Linked to the four strategic components identified, the major goals and methods to realise sustainability are outlined below:

Component	Strategic Elements	Goals	Method
Market	Stakeholders' needs are clearly identified and addressed in a target-oriented way.	The partnership will listen to the needs of the main stakeholders and address them, to create long-term impact.	Consortium presence in academic and industry conversations via conference and forum attendance, interviews with stakeholders.
People	People are put in the centre of the project.	The partnership will put special emphasis on the feeling of "ownership" of the results, that the different stakeholders grow the willingness to drive the capacity building and knowledge exchange from Accelerate Future HEI beyond the project lifetime.	Ensuring the presence of stakeholder's voices within project publications, e.g., as article authorship, launching stakeholder feedback mechanisms for the continuous improvement of project outputs.
Implementation	Implementation of results is made as easy as possible.	The partnership will put special emphasis on reducing implementation barriers.	Involvement of Lead Practitioners team in consultation and training needs of the stakeholders, clear representation of the outputs and guidelines freely available online.
Structural	Right structures are put in place and can be maintained in an efficient way.	The partnership will develop efficient structures so that the project can be further promoted at low costs and effort.	Integration of the project and its results in an open-source platform.

Process

The project outcomes will outlive the project by means of measures taken during the project. To achieve the regular review and update of this document, consortium partners will take advantage of face-to-face and online partner meetings to identify opportunities and develop concrete models to sustain the impact of the project. Particularly, 2 workshops will be organised by UIIN to this specific exercise. In addition, feedback from participants during development of the road maps, pilot testing and capacity-building events will also provide insights into sustainability activities.

The timeline below provides key milestones for the development of the dissemination and sustainability plan.

	M6	M12	M30	M48
Initial Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan	MMS			
IPR Agreement	UIIN			
Updated Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan and Initial Report		MMS		
Workshop 1		UIIN		
Interim Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Report			MMS	
Workshop 2			UIIN	
Final Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Report				MMS

Activities

The Sustainability plan seeks to extend the learnings of the participating HEIs who will have:

1. Developed a strong internal understanding of their status quo and desired future state.
2. Developed and executed their roadmap and subsequently their Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs)
3. Been supported with implementing their ITAPs
4. Received expert coaching, training and peer learning in a network that will sustain beyond the scope of the project.

Partners who have undertaken the process of ITAP implementation will utilise their newly developed learnings from coaching and training in their everyday work, continuing to cascade training and insights to their peers and popularising the Accelerate Future HEI programme. Partner institutions will serve as contact points for parties interested in building on the project approach and outputs.

During the project lifetime, we will build a **network**, that will aim to connect the participating HEIs and their stakeholders. We envision that the Accelerate Future HEI network and established relationships will not cease to exist after the finalisation of the project. We believe that this tight-knit informal community of HEI participants will establish a basis for more formalised networks in each region.

Like-minded organisations, networks and think tanks may be interested in utilising and replicating the result of the project internationally. Some examples include Triple Helix Association, Advance HE, CHE, CHEPS, Guni Network, UIDP, EIT, EINS, INCORE and others. Through our existing partners we are certain to reach the other projects and partners within EIT HEI Initiative, [E³UDRES²](#), INCORE and European Universities Alliances to seek further synergies in our activities.

The **project website** will be maintained for 3 years after the project's completion and will be designed to serve as a promotion platform for both training models and generated resources.

Conference/ forum appearances – in addition to encouraging all partner institutions to present the results of the project at conferences and forums in the field, we will ensure a special track related to the project target focus at the University-Industry Interaction Conference (UIIN), which is attended by 500+ change-makers from HEIs and industries every year. The UIIN conference is a fruitful platform for reaching out to the relevant stakeholders

Social networks will be kept active after the project ends to be used as promotion platforms for the Accelerate Future HEI programmes to reach practitioners at the HEIs and continuous professional development intermediaries in EU and non-EU countries

Instruments

All 20 public deliverables created during the 48-month lifetime of the project will be designed to ultimately be used by the target audience and stakeholders after the completion of the project.

The **networking database** that the partners establish during the project will continue to serve as a regional and wide European network, allowing participants and other stakeholders to interact while project partners adding new contacts to their regional databases as they receive new registrations and participants to their events.

Beneficiaries from the **project** will be registered to the online network database as ‘peer mentors’, who will provide guidance and support to other HEIs looking to bring transformation to their institutions.

Established **relationships with similar networks/organisation**, such as Triple Helix Association, Advance HE, CHE, CHEPS, Guni Network, UIDP, EIT, and EINS for disseminating and sustaining the results of the project.

The project results will be further disseminated through **conferences** that will host specific tracks where experiences from the implementation can be shared and discussed among HEIs, the stakeholders, and other relevant regional actors. (e.g., UIIN Conference, etc.)

Project Website will be maintained for 3 years and updated by Momentum after the project ends and redesigned to serve as a promotion platform for the multimedia project outputs, and the integrated consultancy network. The platform will also have available marketing materials for HEIs and intermediary organisations to promote the Accelerate Future HEI training modules among business consultants as well as among their students and academics, and local SMEs and start-ups. The platform will be designed to permit updating and to support communication from users and stakeholders. The project outputs, available at the Online Resource Platform, will be in free open access. To ensure access, digitalized resources will also be transferred to video and other file-sharing websites, i.e., YouTube, SlideShare, LinkedIn, etc.

Social networks will be kept active after the project ends to be used as promotion platforms for project outputs and upcoming events.

Scientific publications based on the project results in scientific or practitioners’ journals and/or at international conferences.

Press releases, social media postings and multimedia content will inform the media outlets of the project outcomes released on the website and each consortium partner’s websites.

04

Appendices

APPENDIX ONE - PARTNER REACH DATABASE

PARTNER NAME
PARTNER NAME

PERSON LEADING YOUR DISSEMINATION

YOUR NETWORK	NUMBER OF ORGANISATIONS YOU WILL CONNECT Accelerate Future HEI with	Profile of your network

YOUR DATABASE	NUMBER OF SUBSCRIBERS	Profile of subscribers

YOUR ORGANISATION WEBSITE	ADDRESS	REACH – typical monthly reach

SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS	ADDRESS	REACH – number of followers
TWITTER – organisational and personal (if relevant)		
LINKEDIN - organisational and personal for all contributors to the project		
LINKEDIN - please list the groups of which you are a member and can disseminate Accelerate Future HEI		
Professional blog		
Other, please specify		

APPENDIX TWO BLOG POSTS SCHEDULE

Each partner will be charged with creating a **minimum of 2 blog posts per year** and must complete the following blog post contribution template. In addition to highlighting internal expertise, we will invite articles and contributions from Associate Partners/Other Experts. This is a living document with updated versions found in the WP7 Dissemination folder in SharePoint [Appendix 2 OPINION LEADER BLOG POST SCHEDULE.docx \(sharepoint.com\)](#)

Partner	Blog/Article Author	Topics Relevant to Accelerate Future HEI that you will cover	Delivery Date 22 nd of each month April – October 2023	Access to external experts
UNIVERSITY INDUSTRY INNOVATION NETWORK (UIIN)			July	
TUM INTERNATIONAL GMBH			June	
MOMENTUM			April	
INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TECNICO			September	
UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION			June	
UNIVERSIDAD EUROPEA DE CANARIAS SL			October	
UNIVERSIDADE DE MADEIRA			August	
FACHHOCHSCHULE ST. POLTEN GMBH			September	
UC LEUVEN			May	
MAGYAR AGRAR- ES ELETUDOMANYI EGYETEM			August	
UNIVERSITATEA POLITEHNICA TIMISOARA			July	
VIDZEMES AUGSTSKOLA			May	

APPENDIX THREE EZINE ARTICLE SCHEDULE

Each partner will create and contribute articles to the ezines according to the schedule below. The schedule is available to download from SharePoint here [Appendix 3 Accelerate Future HEI Dissemination Plan.docx \(sharepoint.com\)](#)

Schedule for Partner Ezine Contributions					
	About each partner blog	Ezine 1 contribution (December 2023)	Ezine 2 contribution (December 2024)	Ezine 3 contribution (December 2025)	Ezine 4 contribution (December 2026)
UNIVERSITY INDUSTRY INNOVATION NETWORK (UIIN)					
TUM INTERNATIONAL GMBH					
MOMENTUM					
INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TECNICO					
UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION					
UNIVERSIDAD EUROPEA DE CANARIAS SL					
UNIVERSIDADE DE MADEIRA					
FACHHOCHSCHULE ST. POLTEN GMBH					
UC LEUVEN					
MAGYAR AGRAR- ES ELETTUDOMANYI EGYETEM					
UNIVERSITATEA POLITEHNICA TIMISOARA					
VIDZEMES AUGSTSKOLA					

This schedule highlights the planned contributions, however ad-hoc articles for the website, especially related to project implementation activities in partner countries (or external articles that are of interest), will be gathered throughout the project life-time additionally.

APPENDIX FOUR PARTNER DISSEMINATION RECORD

Each partner will complete their dedicated sheet on the Dissemination Record which is in the WP7 Dissemination Folder in SharePoint [Appendix 4- Partner Dissemination Record.xlsx \(sharepoint.com\)](#)

	Posts in Social Media		Blog Article Publication		Magazine	Direct distribution	Hosting/ participating events	
	Twitter	LinkedIn	Project Website	Other Channels		via email	Local	International
Overall Goal	2+ Tweets per month	1+ post per month	As per blog schedule	Open	Downloads	Contact Lists	Workshops	National Events
Reporting Period								
January 2023 - June2023								
July 2023 - December 2023								
January 2024 - June2024								
July 2024 - December 2024								
January 2025 - June2025								
July 2025 - December 2025								
January 2026 - June2026								
July 2026 - December 2026								

Deliverable 7.2
Communications
Dissemination and
Sustainability Plan
Initial Report.

Funded by
the European Union

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- 02** Summary
- 03** Key Activities and Targets
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Details

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01

Introduction

Introduction

This Communications Dissemination and Sustainability Plan Initial Report (D7.2) reviews the dissemination activities of the Accelerate Future HEI Horizon Europe project for the first 12 months of operation from January 2023 to December 2023 as outlined within the original application and Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability plan (D7.1.).

It includes a summary of the main activities as well as a short overview of the dissemination strategy used, based on the Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability plan. It highlights the project targets, the stakeholders and the target audience. It then goes on to report on the key performance indicators from the project against the targets including a performance review of the two social media channels used: LinkedIn and Twitter as well as including performance metrics from the project’s dedicated website.

It outlines the dissemination plans for the project over the next 12 months of the project. Partner content is included as part of the dissemination reporting and examples are highlighted to show where success has been achieved.

Deliverables		Due Date
D7.1	Initial Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Plan	M6
D7.2	Updated Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Plan & Initial Report	M12
D7.3	Interim Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Report	M30
D7.4	Final Interim Communication Dissemination & Sustainability Report	M48

What is a Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan?

The overall objectives of the WP 7 Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan are:

- To **create awareness and understanding** of the importance of Entrepreneurial and Innovative Universities.
- To **raise awareness** about acceleration services and methodologies.
- **Support the integration** of all stakeholders in the different phases of the project.
- **Widely disseminate** the project results and outputs.
- **Set the foundation** for further implementation/exploitation of the results of the project.

We understand Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability as follows;

Stakeholders and Target Groups

Promotion and awareness-raising is an important part of the communications and dissemination process. It is key the project is delivered to its primary target audiences. Target audiences are engaged with messages that will be specifically tailored to them via the project's multiple channels.

The **Accelerate Future HEI** project includes primary target groups and stakeholders of influence who participate in and benefit from the project. To generate and exploit the maximum value of the project, the Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan is responsive to the needs of our key target groups and focuses on the respective channels, and multipliers to reach the target groups, the material and messages delivered, as well as the type and frequency of the communication intended.

The project methodology and underlying processes predefine the development of open-access methodologies and a showcase of results. With these open-access deliverables, we are creating a direct impact on the stakeholder groups outside of the testing HEI partners.

CORE TARGET GROUPS

- HEI Testing Partners
 - HEI Leadership
- Non-academic/Professional Staff
- Academic Staff/Lecturers/Researcher
 - Students & Life-Long Learners

EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS

- Other HEIs (national, regional, local and European levels)
 - Industrial partners, SMEs and startups
- Public bodies (Local, regional, national and European), including municipalities, departments of education, governmental support offices for higher education/entrepreneurship/regional development, etc. Network organisations (local, regional, national and European) entrepreneurship and innovation ecosystem drivers Policy makers, policy advocates and thought leaders

Targets and Measuring Impact

Central to the project Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan is communicating the project's benefits and outcomes and ensuring engagement with the key target groups and regional, national and international stakeholders for a long-lasting impact of the project.

The project's Communications, Dissemination and Sustainability plan's success will be measured against the following criteria for final evaluation:

- Proper use of communication channels and materials to reach the end user and target groups.
- Whether the target audiences were reached and engaged
- To what extent the project's results are known and used outside the project consortium
- How users and stakeholders judge the value of outputs.
- What impact are outputs having upon the practice and understanding of target audiences and what are the prospects for further impact in the future?
- To what extent has sustainability been secured, and external recognition achieved?

02 Summary

Summary

Accelerate Future HEI has a robust Communication, Dissemination and Sustainability Plan. It outlines all the planned activities to reach and engage the target audience over the four-year project duration. This initial report shows that the first stage of activities to raise awareness has been achieved and a strong brand firmly established. They include the creation of the Accelerate Future HEI brand, branded promotional materials, a dedicated website and two social media channels. The project is kept up-to-date with regular blog posts (16) and news items. Both the video and project brochure provide alternative channels to easily and quickly learn about the project.

The project has been successful in raising awareness amongst our target audience. This has been shown in the significant traffic on the project website (9,097 unique visitors), the strong level of interest in the social media channels (369 followers between both channels) and the positive levels of engagement so far. This project speaks to a very specific audience that is not the usual target audience of social media. The project’s social media channels posted 123 times which resulted in 20,919 impressions. For this reason, the project has generated significant interest among other institutions and there is certainly an unmet need for more social media presence when it comes to this topic among HEIs.

Blog posts	Unique Website Visitors	Social Media Posts	Impressions
16	9,097	123	20,919

Accelerate Future HEI has been successful in reaching out to two sister Horizon Europe projects, aUPaEU and CATALISI to form a communications alliance and leverage wider interest and also agree to cross-promotional activities via social media, website and ezine content. Reports on surveys and focus group interviews, which were prepared as qualitative reports with attractive visuals highlighted the most important information and proved valuable for internal communication to those involved in the University and helped to communicate about the project’s progress.

Over the next 12 months through the rollout of the first deliverables and the development of the roadmaps and each partner’s Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects, we will build further desire among our stakeholders with engaging, insightful content. We will shortly see the publication of the first ezine which will be utilised to promote and share the project widely. The creation of infographics and partner videos will offer new multimedia ways of engaging our target audience. We will also increase our focus on blog posts, increasing web traffic and social media impressions.

It is evident from the partner dissemination activities below that the involvement of the partners is key to success, so we aim to include them even more and increase the project’s reach through their institutional communication channels.

Blog posts	LinkedIn	X	Partner Website	Other	Social Media Posts	Impressions	Direct Distribution via email	Local events/ workshops	International Events
22	42	49	7	4	104	356,868	3	18	17

03

Key Activities & Targets

What have we delivered over the first 12 months?

This report is focused on the project website, design and promotional materials. An information brochure was designed, elaborated, and printed to keep the target group and the general public informed about the objectives, the project activities, the participants in the project, and the main expected results. This is available in paper format for its dissemination at events, conferences, and meetings, among other occasions, and also in digital format for its download in PDF format ready to be shared. An informative pop-up poster was also prepared with the same purpose, in digital format for its dissemination at events, conferences, and meetings, among other occasions.

The project has been disseminated through the Accelerate Future HEI website for which the necessary graphic material has been developed: adaptation of images, deliverables, and soon the reports of results for WP2. Apart from the brochure, the poster, and the graphic material for the web, several materials have been created to disseminate the project, the objectives, and the results obtained.

- 1) Website launched supported by press releases for partners to use across all channels.
- 2) Website monthly updates by Momentum to include news, new documents to be made available for download, information on events etc. at each monthly meeting.
- 3) Image bank created - Collected and provided access to license-free images to reflect the specific target groups.
- 4) Momentum created a specific Social Media Content Kit for Twitter and LinkedIn.
- 5) Partners contributed to profiling their Reach Database – see Appendix 1 on AFH SharePoint, sharing details of their dissemination reach.
- 6) All partners contributed to the development and update of the project website blog and news section, highlighting the developments within the scope of the project in their region. Partners can translate the content for dissemination for national purposes.
- 7) Each partner displays news about the project on their respective official websites and include the news about the project and the project's developments in their newsletters to reach their regional stakeholders.

Project Brand

To Raise Awareness amongst HEI internal and external stakeholders about the importance of an entrepreneurial approach inside and outside of the university.

Building Awareness is the first phase of our approach as we seek to build up an engaged community around Accelerate Future HEI.

Brand Building

Momentum has created a strong professional and engaging project brand and intent tagline. This is the first step in the visibility creation of the project under our Communication ambition. The brand is also available in an animated format, as presented on the project website:

<https://acceleratefuturehei.eu/>

Key brand features include: -

- Text-based brands are known to lead to brand longevity. The brand emphasises the word accelerate, and the future-focused project ambition by using an upward forward-facing arrow design.
- The colour combination of red and black balances positive energy balanced with intent. The primary colour red gives positive energy while black adds certainty and authority.
- Our brand is leading out on a series of design templates and promotional materials (flyers, logos, signs and banners).
- Our brand guidelines will be used by project partners to ensure brand consistency across: -
 - Brand and brand usage
 - Colour specifications
 - Typography
 - Use of trademark symbols

Promotion Materials

The first phase of marketing collateral created (months 1 to 6), encompasses a series of marketing tools that allow us to reach large audiences in a short period. They included:-

- Brand Manual & logo
- 1-page project summary.
- 5 slides project presentation, in editable PowerPoint format and created as an introductory video
- Project brochure (awareness building theme) * to illustrate key project concepts using infographics and visual aids. The project brochure will be uploaded in electronic PDF format onto the project website as from its production and it will be easy to download and share.
- Infographics summarising the project results as are striving for – Our Ambition at a Glance
- Project roll-up banner
- Project e-zine template.
- Project reports template.
- Event-specific project flyers, for various events
- Online banners including branded social media headers, placeholders etc. *
- Graphics to support partner dissemination e.g., our badge of honour

All WP 7 shared content can be found at the following link for the duration of the project: [WP7](#)

Example flyer created

JOIN OUR ROADMAP WORKSHOP

The Roadmap Workshop is part of the research phase of the EU-funded Horizon Accelerate Future HEI four-year project aiming to **develop and test acceleration services**, to equip HEIs with the skills and capacity to drive institutional transformation towards becoming more **entrepreneurial and innovative institutions**.

Thinking along the lines of becoming more entrepreneurial and innovative and reflecting on the desired future scenario, how will we get there? During the **Roadmap Workshop**, internal stakeholders across our HEI, will get together to discuss our key challenges and ideate and prioritise solutions that could help us achieve our institutional transformation.

Based on workshop results, UIIN will summarise the key initiatives, which will be the foundation for us to develop our **Institutional Transformation Acceleration Projects (ITAPs)** and guide the transformation agenda. Please contribute to the conversation and join us in transforming our university.

accelerate future HEI
supporting future focused higher education

Who should participate?

To gain a holistic perspective, the focus group should have representation across different internal stakeholder groups. Suggested participant profiles include (at least 10 consisting of a mixture of):

- **University or Faculty leadership**, e.g. rector, vice-rectors, Deans, Heads of Departments etc.
- **Professional or Administrative staff** responsible for supporting different activities and areas of external engagement, innovation and entrepreneurship.
- **Academic staff or researchers** who are involved in entrepreneurship, engagement and innovation activities as part of their teaching or research.

Note: the identified participants should be familiar with the project and ideally will be part of the team that will drive the project forward.

How will it take place?

The **Roadmap Workshop** will take place **online via Zoom** and will run for **2.5-3 hours**. This will be a facilitated discussion, led by UIIN, who will guide the group through a series of questions, using an online collaboration tool called **Mural**.

In this **interactive session**, you will be guided through a structured canvas and work collaboratively to provide concrete ideas for an acceleration development roadmap towards institutional transformation. This will be aligned with the transformation agenda and based on the current state and strategic visions of testing partners to become an Entrepreneurial and Innovative University.

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UIIN
University of Innovation and Innovation

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Project Website

Momentum has established an engaging project website <https://acceleratefuturehei.eu/> reflecting our corporate design. The website is the central access point for the project. All data generated during the course of the project is made available through a project website- which is continuously updated.

The project website will spread awareness and share information about the project and will be kept active for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

The main features of the website are: -

- A dynamic and engaging landing page and a selection of subpages highlighting the main information about the project and contact details of the partners.
- Mobile friendly design
- Use of best practice web development, SEO optimisation, integration with different media formats, e.g., infographics, videos, and presentations to create a dynamic intuitive environment for all visitors.
- Incorporation of resources repository with all materials and outputs of the project in easily downloadable format.
- Source of downloadable marketing materials (e.g., posters, flyers) to equip all stakeholders to promote the project outcomes and both training programmes and toolkits.
- We will publish annual mini-e-zine series available for free download. Four issues are to be published during the project lifetime.
- Publishing articles about the main project outputs, content and promotion of the training programmes, and project events will occur on the project website.
- All WP deliverables will be available for download and form the basis of dissemination activity via shorter engaging articles and posts.

The project website is updated regularly by Momentum to keep visitors engaged by highlighting recent news within the scope of the project from global and European outlets.

Download Our Brochure

Join us on the journey of HEI transformation and innovation to discover how **Accelerate Future HEI** will develop and test acceleration services, to equip HEIs with the skills and capacity to support and drive institutional change.

[Download Brochure](#)

9,097: No. of Unique website visitors to 21st December 2023

Users by Country

The majority of traffic is from the US, Portugal, the Netherlands, Ireland and Spain. The website hosts blog post news items (#16) including a project video and brochure.

Source: Google Analytics

Blogposts

Partners have actively been involved in contributing blog posts to the project website. We have used the blog posts to update the project stakeholders about the ‘entrepreneurial university journey’ featuring partner profiles, institution events and project workshops and meetings. Momentum has worked closely with the two Horizon Europe sister projects to cross-promote their events and activities. MMS and Partners will continue to identify opportunities to engage with the target audience and build awareness through these activities.

[A sample of the 16 blog posts available to view here on the project website: News - Accelerate Future HEI](#)

Here's our latest news and updates.

<p>Introducing our sister project – aUPaEU</p> <p>Accelerate Future HEI is a Horizon Europe project funded under the HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-S1 call. This call funds the development of Acceleration Services in support of the</p> <p>READ MORE »</p> <p>November 10, 2023</p>		
<p>UIIN: A Decade of Pioneering University Transformation</p> <p>Since 2012, UIIN has been driving the transformation of the higher education sector. Its mission is to make universities more disruptive, impactful, and engaged with</p> <p>READ MORE »</p> <p>October 23, 2023</p>		
<p>Accelerate Future HEI Partners gather online for Transnational Partner Meeting</p> <p>The second Transnational Partner Meeting (TPM) of the Accelerate Future HEI project took place on June 29th. Representatives of partners from across Europe gathered online</p> <p>READ MORE »</p> <p>August 25, 2023</p>		

Social Media

Dedicated social media platforms (Twitter, LinkedIn) are kept active every week by posting news about the project and sharing the news from external news channels within the thematic scope of the project to build awareness with stakeholders.

Partners assist with target audience recruitment and with identifying social media accounts to engage with. Project partners are included in social media posting, including associated alliances @incore_eu @eudres_alliance @REA_research @HorizonEU

LinkedIn The following LinkedIn page has been set up [Accelerate Future HEI: Overview | LinkedIn](#)

Twitter The following Twitter account has been set up [AccelerateFutureHEI \(@AccFutureHEI\) / Twitter](#)

We are using the following Hashtags in social media posts to help amplify our messaging.

- #AccFutureHEI
- #HorizonEU
- #highereducationinnovation
- #REA (research executive agency)

As part of the social media strategy, we ensure:

Project partners are steered towards a unified approach to strategic social media sharing and tagging in their expansive networks that will contribute to building our project visibility. To achieve this, a detailed professional **'Social Media Content Kit'** was shared with the partners that informed them about the key target groups (including their specific interests and values), type of content (short and long copy), frequency of posting and key hashtags, design, style, and length of the language to be used for each of the social media channels.

Social media links are provided from the main page of the project website to keep visitors updated with real-time information and the opportunity to share and reshare the latest developments of the project.

Calls to action to follow the Accelerate Future HEI social media accounts are published on the project brochures and flyers. Social media is designed for conversation, not for announcements. To be effective, we have committed to regularly posting across our channels and engaging in topic-based contributions as appropriate. We encourage everyone involved in the project to join in the conversation so that multiple points of view are reflected.

The social media channel metrics for both Twitter and LinkedIn demonstrate positive reach and engagement achieved in the first year of the project with both channels boasting active engagement demonstrated through likes, retweets, comments and reposting of content. Project partners used their institution's social media accounts including the above, Facebook and Instagram.

X/Twitter

- **149 Tweets**
- **56 Followers**

A sample of recently posted content

LinkedIn

- **313 Followers**
- **812 Reactions**
- **11 Comments**
- **43 Shares**
- **661 Page Views**
- **301 Unique Visitors**
- **20 Custom Button Clicks**

A sample of recently posted content

Accelerate Future HEI
313 followers
3d • 🌐

Join us on the journey of HEI transformation and innovation to discover how **Accelerate Future HEI** will develop and test acceleration services, to equip HEIs with the skills and capacity to support and drive institutional change.

Download our brochure here: <https://lnkd.in/d7jbi4q7>

#highereducation #Innovation #entrepreneurship #development
#AccelerateFutureHEI

Download Our Brochure

accelerate futureHEI
supporting future focused higher education

You and 13 others
2 reposts

Reactions

Accelerate Future HEI
313 followers
1mo • 🌐

Join us in our upcoming Policy Recommendation Workshop, where we extend a warm welcome to public stakeholders, policymakers, policy advocates, and thought leaders actively engaged in higher education innovation and regional development. ...see more

JOIN OUR POLICY RECOMMENDATION WORKSHOP

📅 1st OF DECEMBER 2023
🕒 10:00 - 11:30 CET
📺 ONLINE VIA ZOOM

UIN University Industry Innovation Network
Funded by the European Union
accelerate futureHEI supporting future focused higher education

You and 16 others
4 reposts

👤 You
👍 Like
💬 Comment
🔄 Repost
➦ Send

Multimedia Content

We prioritise digital media content and approaches, Momentum has created a short promotional video introducing the project, our partnership, and our activities. Additional promotional videos and short-form video content will be produced at key stages of the project to utilise this visual media to share updates and flag activities and events. A series of nine short videos about transformation (one per testing partner) will also be created. Attractive videos will be posted on the project website and relayed through YouTube and LinkedIn platforms for maximum visibility. Where appropriate, Momentum will add podcasts and audio material as well as host virtual events through the website to ensure a mix of multimedia content throughout the project's lifetime

[View the AFH video here: Accelerate Future HEI - Supporting Future Focused Higher Education \(youtube.com\)](#)

Accelerate Future HEI - Supporting Future Focused Higher Education

Ezines

In year two, 2024 as we enter Phase 2 of the ADKAR approach, we will create a desire amongst our target groups to participate in the activities that lead to a more entrepreneurial culture within and outside the university.

Establishing consistent communication with target groups via our partner's extensive contact databases will be key for a pan-European approach. In this way, rather than trying to build the **Accelerate Future HEI** community from the ground up, we can benefit from already existing communities and build upon those. These include social media communities (i.e. UIIN, TUM Int., MMS, UE, UPT, MATE, UMA, UCLL, STPUAS, UR, IST, ViA), EU-level networks (INCORE, EU3DRES2, EINS and European Research Executive Agency & Horizon Europe), and country-level networks. By tapping into these channels and sharing the project's activities/outputs we will increase the outreach to the target groups (e.g., universities, academics, researchers, students, industry, etc.)

Accelerate Future HEI Ezine Series

Momentum has been working to prepare the first of four annual ezines, which is due for publication in February 2024. We have created a bespoke branded ezine template and all partners are creating content in line with an agreed content plan. The topics selected for inclusion in the ezine introduce the scope and aim of the project, introduce some of the partners, outline our work to date and report on the current state analysis work being carried out in WP2. We also introduce our two Horizon Europe sister projects.

The ezine series will be circulated directly and available for download in PDF format with open access. To support distribution of the ezines we have designed a dedicated space on the project website where all four ezines will be hosted and available to download. We have also set up a GDPR-compliant integrated email subscription facility on the website to create a project-specific database. Invitations to subscribe are scheduled for social media promotion in January and then throughout the project's lifetime. The news of the ezine launch, with a link to download, will also be promoted on the project's social media channels and with a blog post on the website.

The ezine series will be circulated widely via partner newsletters and channels, project subscribers updates, project social media, and the project website as well as on external resource/news-sharing platforms. While partners and their networks will be core disseminators, we invite partners to suggest additional platforms.

Scientific Publications

There is a strong opportunity for partners to utilise scientific publications as part of their dissemination activities. Many of the participating University team members are researchers for whom international scientific publications are an important part of their work and career. During the first year of the project, a large amount of data has already been obtained, which can be analyzed from a scientific point of view, interpreted and shared via academic research publications. In addition, the publications also give prestige to the participating Universities, as well as help to spread the results of the project more widely. Publication in internationally recognised and prestigious journals can bolster dissemination efforts and bring the project findings to our target audience.

European Commission Channels

The project will also look to share its results via the many European Commission free-of-charge services to support our dissemination and exploitation activities:

Open Research Europe platform: An open-access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article revision.

Horizon Results platform: A platform for showcasing your research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others.

Horizon Results Booster: Free consulting services including a portfolio dissemination and exploitation strategy, business plan development and go-to-market support.

Success stories will be championed through some of the European Commission's free-of-charge channels such as:

- [Cordis Results in Brief](#),
- [CORDIScovery podcasts](#),
- [Research & innovation success storiesEN●●●](#)
- [Horizon Magazine](#) or
- during events such as the [R&I Days](#).

Main Project Deliverables

In early 2024, the project will add the first two deliverables, D2.1 and D2.2 from WP2 to the project website for public dissemination once they have gone through the final review stages.

WP2: Identifying and publishing individual reports for each stakeholder and one synthesis report to understand the current state and desired future state of each testing partner and provide an evidence base for entrepreneurial and innovative activities.

Main Deliverables

Management, QA & Policy Feedback M1 – M48 <i>The plan for how we will ensure we deliver on our outcomes & inform policy</i>	D1.1 DMP M6	D1.2 Initial policy briefing M12	D1.3 Interim policy briefing M30	D1.4 Final policy recommendations report M48
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Current State Analysis M1 – M12 <i>Uncovering the goals for institutional transformation. Where are HEIs now?</i>	Developing Roadmaps & ITAPs M6-M18 <i>What needs to change to achieve the goals and how will you do it?</i>		Acceleration services pilot-testing M12 – M48 <i>What will you test and implement?</i>	
	D2.1 Strategic Vision Statements – M12	D2.2 Synthesis Report – M12	D3.1 Roadmaps Analysis report – Draft M12	D3.2 Roadmaps Analysis report – Final M18

Capacity Building & Knowledge Exchange Program M1 – M48 <i>The plan for how HEIs gain skills and insights for acceleration & transformation</i>	D5.1 Program overview & delivery plan M12	D5.2 Program delivery progress report & updated plan M30	D5.3 Summary of the learning outcomes M48
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Acceleration Impact – Monitoring & Evaluation M1 – M48 <i>We will monitor progress and evaluate impact of ITAPs</i>	D6.1 Monitoring & evaluation plan – M12	D6.2 ITAPs Progress report – M30	D6.3 Final Impact Report
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Communication and Dissemination M1 – M48 <i>We plan to share our key learnings so others can benefit</i>	D7.1 Initial Plan M6	D7.2 Updated plan and initial dissemination report M12	D7.3 Interim dissemination report M30	D7.4 Final dissemination report M48
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04

Appendices

Partner Dissemination

To realise and reinforce the overall dissemination of the Accelerate Future HEI project, as dissemination lead Momentum

- Includes the feedback of all partners on its dissemination activities
- Welcomes all feedback and input from partners in the creation and sharing of promotional materials.
- Requires all partners to register their activities in a communication reporting document and share it with Momentum every 6 months. All partners save evidence of their activities to assess if actions are being carried out and to see what activities had the biggest impact on the stakeholders.

Any feedback and partner reporting were considered for inclusion in the Dissemination Partner updates. All Appendices are completed by partners and kept on the SharePoint link for continuous reference and review.

On the following pages, the report of all dissemination activities of partners is presented, as a quick overview of the various kinds of dissemination activities, a description, dates when the activity took place, location, dissemination level, target group, number of people reached and the proof of the activity: [Appendix 4- Partner Dissemination Record.xlsx](#)

accelerate futureHEI

supporting future focused higher education

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Journey

www.acceleratefuturehei.eu

